

An equivalent beam approach for assessing tunnelling-induced distortions of frames with infills

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Supplemental data

Figure S1: Contours of tensile strains in the infills panels of the long central two-storey frame (FRs2e0L) at $V_{it} = 1.0\%$: (left) fully flexible panels, (right) stiff panels.

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Figure S2: Plaxis and ASRE tensile strain (FRs2e0L)

Figure S3: Plaxis and ASRE tensile strain (FRs2e0L)